

A Systematic Critical Review of *Kaiyadev Nighantu* with Conceptual Insights

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ABSTRACT

Introduction- A *Nighantu* is a glossary of names used to identify Ayurvedic substances.^[1] *Kaiyadeva Nighantu*, stands out for integrating medicine, diet and lifestyle in a unified framework. It is a classical Ayurvedic lexicon that systematically describes medicinal, dietary and lifestyle-related substances. It presents a concise and practical classification of *dravyas*, highlighting their nomenclature and therapeutic relevance. The text remains important for accurate drug identification and holistic *Ayurvedic* practice.

Methodology- The review is based on classical *Ayurvedic* texts, *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* and relevant scholarly literature.

Results- *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* classifies substances into eight Vargas: *Aushadhi*, *Dhatu-Dhanya*, *Drava*, *Mamsa*, *Krita-Anna*, *Vihara*, *Mishraka* and *Nanarthaka*, covering medicines, foods, liquids, lifestyle factors, and polysemous terms.

Discussion- The text provides a clear and holistic classification useful for clinical practice, though some descriptions require modern scientific correlation.

Conclusion- *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* remains a concise and relevant reference for *Ayurvedic* drug identification and integrated health practice.

KEY WORDS: *Kaiyadeva Nighantu*, *Dravyaguna*, *Varga*

INTRODUCTION

Nighantu means a “collection of names” and is described as a vocabulary or glossary essential for the correct identification of drugs. Classical texts compare a physician without the knowledge of *Nighantu* to a scholar without grammar or an archer without practice.^[1]

Kaiyadeva Nighantu was composed after earlier lexicons such as *Dhanwantari Nighantu*^[2], *Madanpal Nighantu*^[3], *Amarkosha*^[4] and *Bhojraj Kosha*^[5]. While it reflects the foundational structure of earlier *Nighantus*, *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* introduces a more practical and concise approach by including not only medicinal plants but also food substances, liquids, metals, lifestyle factors, and compound formulations. In this way, it overcomes several limitations of previous *Nighantus* by expanding the scope of *Dravyaguna* to encompass daily diet and conduct along with therapeutics.^[6]

Kaiyadeva Nighantu was authored by *Acharya Kaiyadeva*, a renowned *Ayurvedic* scholar of the medieval period. Although limited biographical details are available, his work reflects profound clinical

insight and scholastic mastery over *Dravyaguna* and *Ahara-Vihara* concepts. The text demonstrates the author's intention to provide a user-friendly reference for physicians by presenting substances in a systematic and function-oriented manner rather than an overly elaborate descriptive style.^[7]

The distinguishing feature of *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* lies in its well-defined *varga* classification, which includes *Aushadhi*, *Dhatu*, *Dhanya*, *Drava*, *Mamsa*, *Krita-Anna*, *Vihara* and *Mishraka Vargas*. This arrangement highlights the integrated *Ayurvedic* view that medicine, diet, and lifestyle together maintain health and cure disease.^[7] Thus, *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* serves as a compact yet comprehensive guide for accurate drug identification and rational clinical application.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This narrative review is based on the critical study of *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* along with references from other classical *Nighantus*, *Ayurvedic Samhitas*, commentaries and standard *Dravyaguna* literature. Relevant research articles and Ayurvedic pharmacological sources were also consulted to understand the conceptual and practical significance of the text.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

The primary source of information for the present study is *Kaiyadeva Nighantu*, which systematically presents *dravyas* under eight major Vargas. The text emphasizes the classification of substances according to their utility- medicinal, dietary, lifestyle-related or compound and clarifies their nomenclature through synonyms and polysemous terms.^[6]

Authorship- *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* was authored by *Acharya Kaiyadeva*, a well-known medieval Ayurvedic scholar. Unlike *Raj Nighantu*, detailed autobiographical references about the author are not found in the text. However, the systematic arrangement of *dravyas* and the practical orientation of the work clearly reflect *Kaiyadeva's* deep scholarship in *Dravyaguna*, *Ahara* and *Vihara*. His approach indicates a clinician-oriented mindset aimed at simplifying drug identification and application for physicians.^[7]

Time Period- *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* does not explicitly mention the date of its composition. On the basis of linguistic style, terminology and conceptual development, scholars place the work in the late medieval period of *Ayurveda*. Comparative studies suggest that it was composed after *Dhanwantari Nighantu*^[2] and *Madanpal Nighantu*^[3], but before some later elaborate lexicons. Most authorities broadly place *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* between the **13th and 15th century CE**, with a stronger inclination toward the **14th century CE**.

Original Name of the Text- The text is traditionally known as *Kaiyadeva Nighantu*, named after its author. Unlike *Raj Nighantu*,^[5] there is no clear evidence of an earlier alternative title mentioned within the text itself. The naming convention follows the common practice of identifying *Nighantus* by their author's name.

Sources and Inspirations- *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* was composed after the study of earlier classical lexicons such as *Dhanwantari Nighantu*^[2], *Madanpal Nighantu*^[3], *Amarkosha*^[4] and other Ayurvedic and Sanskrit vocabularies. While it draws inspiration from these works, *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* differs in its practical classification by incorporating medicinal substances along with food items, liquids, lifestyle factors, and compound preparations. This reflects an advancement over earlier *Nighantus*, which were largely plant-centric.

Manuscripts and Preservation- Manuscripts of *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* are preserved in several prestigious institutions, including:

- Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.
- Saraswati Bhavan Library, Varanasi.
- Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute, Pune.
- Theosophical Society Library, Chennai.

These sources confirm the authenticity and widespread circulation of the text among classical scholars.

Structure and Varga System- *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* adopts a concise and functional *Varga* system. The text is divided into eight major Vargas: [7]

- ***Aushadhi Varga***^[8]- medicinal substances
- ***Dhatu Varga***^[9]- metals and minerals
- ***Dhanya Varga***^[10]- cereals
- ***Drava Varga***^[11]- liquids such as water, milk, ghrita, taila, and madya
- ***Mamsa Varga***^[12]- meat and animal products
- ***Krita-Anna Varga***^[13]- prepared and processed food articles
- ***Vihara Varga***^[14]- lifestyle and behavioral factors
- ***Mishraka Varga***^[15]- compound and mixed preparations

Total content of *Kaiyadev Nighantu* (approx.)- Total *Dravyas*: ≈ 550–600; Medicinal plants alone: ≈ 450

Kaiyadeva Nighantu presents nearly six hundred *dravyas* arranged into eight practical Vargas, integrating **medicine, diet, liquids, lifestyle, and compound formulations**, thereby serving as a concise yet holistic Ayurvedic lexicon. [7]

S. No.	Varga Name	Brief Introduction	Approx. No. of Dravyas	Examples of Dravyas
1	<i>Aushadhi Varga</i> ^[8]	Main section dealing with medicinal plant drugs used for prevention and treatment of diseases.	≈450 plants	<i>Haritaki, Bibhitaki, Amalaki, Guduchi, Shatavari, Ashwagandha, Bala, Punarnava</i>
2	<i>Dhatu Varga</i> ^[9]	Includes metals and minerals having medicinal and nutritional value.	≈57	<i>Swarna, Rajata, Tamra, Loha</i>
3	<i>Dhanya Varga</i> ^[10]	Includes cereals and pulses having medicinal and nutritional value.	≈56	<i>Shali, Yava, Godhuma, Mudga</i>
4	<i>Drava Varga</i> ^[11]	Describes liquid substances important for digestion, nourishment, and as anupana.	8 types	<i>Jala, Dugdha, Dadhi, Takra, Ghrita, Taila, Madhu, Madya</i>
5	<i>Mamsa Varga</i> ^[12]	Covers meat and animal products used mainly as dietary and strength-promoting substances.	≈60	<i>Aja, Mahisha, Mriga, Kukuta, Lava, Kapota, Matsya</i>

6	Krita-Anna Varga ^[13]	Deals with cooked and processed food preparations and their health effects.	≈112	<i>Anna, Odana, Peya, Vilepi, Yavagu, Manda, Modaka</i>
7	Vihara Varga ^[14]	Explains lifestyle, behaviour and daily activities influencing health and disease.	≈52 topics	<i>Nidra, Vyayama, Snana, Abhyanga, Maithuna, Vega-dharana</i>
8	Mishraka Varga ^[15]	Contains compound and mixed preparations used therapeutically and dietetically.	≈116	<i>Triphala, Trikatu, Panchalavana, Ghrita-yoga, Taila-yoga</i>

Aushadhi Varga^[8]

Sr. No.	Drug Name
1	<i>Guduchi</i>
2	<i>Vasa</i>
3	<i>Bilva</i>
4	<i>Agnimanth</i>
5	<i>Gambhari</i>
6	<i>Patala</i>
7	<i>Shyonak</i>
8	<i>Shalaparni</i>
9	<i>Prishniparni</i>
10	<i>Brihati</i>
11	<i>Kantakari</i>
12	<i>Gokshura</i>
13	<i>Brihat Panchamula</i>
14	<i>Laghu Panchamula</i>
15	<i>Dashamula</i>
16	<i>Madhyama Panchamula</i>
17	<i>Jeevana Panchamula</i>
18	<i>Trina Panchamula</i>
19	<i>Valli Panchamula</i>
20	<i>Kantaka Panchamula</i>
21	<i>Ashtavarga</i>
22	<i>Kakoli Kshirakakoli</i>
23	<i>Meda & Mahameda</i>
24	<i>Jivaka & Rishabhaka</i>
25	<i>Riddhi & Vriddhi</i>

26	<i>Jivanti</i>
27	<i>Yasti madhu</i>
28	<i>Mashaparni</i>
29	<i>Mudgaparni</i>
30	<i>Jeevaniya Gana</i>
31	<i>Putrajeev</i>
32	<i>Erand</i>
33	<i>Rakta erand</i>
34	<i>Nirgundi</i>
35	<i>Nala</i>
36	<i>Vansha</i>
37	<i>Ikshu</i>
38	<i>Lohitekshu</i>
39	<i>Anyakshu bheda</i>
40	<i>Ikshu vikara</i>
41	<i>Twraj sharkara</i>
42	<i>Madhu sharkara</i>
43	<i>Guda sharkara</i>
44	<i>Pondraj sharkara</i>
45	<i>Yas sharkara</i>
46	<i>Phanit</i>
47	<i>Madhuk phanit</i>
48	<i>Guda</i>
49	<i>Madhu</i>
50	<i>Samanya madhu guna</i>
51	<i>Vishista madhu guna</i>
52	<i>Makshika Madhu</i>
53	<i>Kshodra Madhu</i>
54	<i>Paittika Madhu</i>

55	<i>Bhramara Madhu</i>
56	<i>Chatra Madhu</i>
57	<i>Dala Madhu</i>
58	<i>Navin Madhu</i>
59	<i>Purana Madhu</i>
60	<i>Sheetoshna madhu guna</i>
61	<i>Madhchshistam</i>
62	<i>Tugakshiri vansh lochan</i>
63	<i>Haritaki</i>
64	<i>Amalaki</i>
65	<i>Vibhitaka</i>
66	<i>Triphala</i>
67	<i>Bhumyamalaki</i>
68	<i>Pracinamalaka</i>
69	<i>Bijapura</i>
70	<i>Madhukarkati</i>
71	<i>Narikel</i>
72	<i>Kadali</i>
73	<i>Kadali Bheda</i>
74	<i>khajur</i>
75	<i>Draksha</i>
76	<i>Dadima</i>
77	<i>Naranga</i>
78	<i>Jambira</i>
79	<i>Amalvetas</i>
80	<i>Saramala</i>
81	<i>Nimbuka</i>
82	<i>Bhavya</i>

83	<i>Amra</i>
84	<i>Jambu</i>
85	<i>Badari</i>
86	<i>Amlika</i>
87	<i>vrikshamala</i>
88	<i>Karamarda</i>
89	<i>Akshodaka</i>
90	<i>Karira</i>
91	<i>Aruka</i>
92	<i>Koshamra</i>
93	<i>Rajadana</i>
94	<i>Rajadana Bheda</i>
95	<i>Priyala</i>
96	<i>Tinduka</i>
97	<i>Vikankata</i>
98	<i>Tanka</i>
99	<i>Amrataka</i>
100	<i>Kapittha</i>
101	<i>Kapittha patra</i>
102	<i>Vata</i>
103	<i>Udumbara</i>
104	<i>Ashvattha</i>
105	<i>phalish</i>
106	<i>Plaksha</i>
107	<i>Kshiri vriksh</i>
108	<i>Nandi vriksh</i>
109	<i>Kakodumbarika</i>
110	<i>Peelu</i>
111	<i>Madhuka</i>
112	<i>Panas</i>
113	<i>Lakush</i>
114	<i>Tala</i>
115	<i>Palevatum</i>
116	<i>Nipa</i>
117	<i>Artagala</i>
118	<i>Tuudam</i>
119	<i>Mriglindika</i>
120	<i>Bhallatak</i>
121	<i>Nadi bhallatak</i>
122	<i>tuvara</i>
123	<i>Vatamadhyaka</i>
124	<i>Elanam</i>
125	<i>Lavali Phala</i>

126	<i>Nagavalli</i>
127	<i>Puga</i>
128	<i>Shakani</i>
129	<i>Phalashakani</i>
130	<i>Karkaru</i>
131	<i>Kalingum</i>
132	<i>Rajalabu</i>
133	<i>Kututumbi</i>
134	<i>Ervavukam</i>
135	<i>Trapusham</i>
136	<i>Chirbhitum</i>
137	<i>Gaja Chirbhitum</i>
138	<i>Chikanum</i>
139	<i>Balukum</i>
140	<i>Aranya trapusham</i>
141	<i>Patola</i>
142	<i>Koshataki</i>
143	<i>Raja Koshataki</i>
144	<i>Maha Koshataki</i>
145	<i>Vrintaka</i>
146	<i>Bimbi</i>
147	<i>Karavellaka</i>
148	<i>Jalakaravellaka</i>
149	<i>Vandhya karkotaki</i>
150	<i>karkotaki</i>
151	<i>Vishamushti</i>
152	<i>Kakandola</i>
153	<i>Kapikachu</i>
154	<i>Pust shimbi</i>
155	<i>Sheleshmatak</i>
156	<i>Vyaghratak</i>
157	<i>Patra shakani</i>
158	<i>Varshuka</i>
159	<i>Jivant</i>
160	<i>Chelli</i>
161	<i>Kala shaak</i>
162	<i>Tanduliya</i>
163	<i>Shvetarakta maarish</i>
164	<i>Vichitra maarish</i>
165	<i>Amla maarish</i>
166	<i>Jalamaarish</i>
167	<i>Latavaaka</i>
168	<i>Sarshap</i>

169	<i>Rajika</i>
170	<i>Chanaka</i>
171	<i>Kalaya</i>
172	<i>Palankya</i>
173	<i>Chanchu</i>
174	<i>Brihat Lonika</i>
175	<i>Loni</i>
176	<i>Kthinjaar</i>
177	<i>Kuntali</i>
178	<i>Tilaparni</i>
179	<i>Phanji</i>
180	<i>Upodaka</i>
181	<i>Bhumipadaka</i>
182	<i>Kurantika</i>
183	<i>Dronapushpi</i>
184	<i>Mulaka</i>
185	<i>Grijana</i>
186	<i>Patha</i>
187	<i>Kuchelika</i>
188	<i>Kasmarda</i>
189	<i>Sunishnaka</i>
190	<i>Vishnukanta</i>
191	<i>Sarpaksi</i>
192	<i>Hilmochika</i>
193	<i>dugdika</i>
194	<i>Changeri</i>
195	<i>Chakramarda</i>
196	<i>Bakuchi</i>
197	<i>Kakmachi</i>
198	<i>Kakjangha</i>
199	<i>Jyotishmati</i>
200	<i>Kaknasa</i>
201	<i>brahmi</i>
202	<i>Suvarchala</i>
203	<i>Matsyashakhi</i>
204	<i>Jalapippali</i>
205	<i>Gojihwa</i>
206	<i>Meshashringi</i>
207	<i>Shigru</i>
208	<i>Punarnava</i>
209	<i>Kathillaka</i>
210	<i>Vetasa</i>
211	<i>Jalavetasa</i>

212	<i>Aakukarni</i>
213	<i>Hamsapadi</i>
214	<i>Nagini</i>
215	<i>Somavalli</i>
216	<i>Chudala</i>
217	<i>Nakuli / Gandhanakuli</i>
218	<i>Nagadamani (Ishwari)</i>
219	<i>Sudarsana</i>
220	<i>Ambashta</i>
221	<i>Murva</i>
222	<i>Morath</i>
223	<i>Nilini</i>
224	<i>Gunja</i>
225	<i>Devadali</i>
226	<i>Utmarini</i>
227	<i>Mahavashpa</i>
228	<i>Shaka</i>
229	<i>Shala</i>
230	<i>Tamala</i>
231	<i>Beejaka</i>
232	<i>Teenish</i>
233	<i>bhurja</i>
234	<i>kakubha</i>
235	<i>Khadir</i>
236	<i>shvet khadir</i>
237	<i>Irimed</i>
238	<i>Eravati</i>
239	<i>kanthari</i>
240	<i>Palasha</i>
241	<i>Dhava</i>
242	<i>Dhanvanga</i>
243	<i>Sarja</i>
244	<i>Ashvakarna</i>
245	<i>Varuna</i>
246	<i>Virtaru</i>
247	<i>vrikshdani</i>
248	<i>Guntha</i>
249	<i>Jinhini</i>
250	<i>shallaki</i>
251	<i>Inguda</i>
252	<i>Kinnihi</i>

253	<i>Katambhara</i>
254	<i>Mokshak</i>
255	<i>Nimba</i>
256	<i>Mahanimba</i>
257	<i>Kiratatikta</i>
258	<i>Kutaja</i>
259	<i>Paribhadra</i>
260	<i>Madana</i>
261	<i>Pindit bheda</i>
262	<i>Shavak</i>
263	<i>Shalmali</i>
264	<i>Rohitaka</i>
265	<i>Sehunda</i>
266	<i>Satala</i>
267	<i>Ankota</i>
268	<i>Ashmantaka</i>
269	<i>Kovidara</i>
270	<i>Kanchanara</i>
271	<i>Agasteek</i>
272	<i>Aragvadha</i>
273	<i>Kampillaka</i>
274	<i>Nandi vriksa</i>
275	<i>Saptaparna</i>
276	<i>Kadamba</i>
277	<i>Kalambika</i>
278	<i>Haridru</i>
279	<i>Karanja</i>
280	<i>Karanjka</i>
281	<i>Kantakaraja</i>
282	<i>Shirisha</i>
283	<i>Devasarshapa</i>
284	<i>Shishampa</i>
285	<i>Shirishiak</i>
286	<i>Arishtaka</i>
287	<i>Durjalabha</i>
289	<i>Shravani</i>
290	<i>Aakashavalli</i>
291	<i>Sariva</i>
292	<i>Krishna sariva</i>
293	<i>Aavartaki</i>
294	<i>Markandika</i>
295	<i>Shanpushpi</i>
296	<i>Danti dravanti</i>

297	<i>Trivrit</i>
298	<i>Shyama</i>
299	<i>Swarnakshiri</i>
300	<i>Kankushtham</i>
301	<i>Indravaruni</i>
302	<i>Trayamana</i>
303	<i>Apamarga</i>
304	<i>Vasheer</i>
305	<i>Ramatha</i>
306	<i>Tejovati</i>
307	<i>Rasna</i>
308	<i>Ashwagandha</i>
309	<i>Saireyak</i>
310	<i>Bal chatushtaya</i>
311	<i>prasarini</i>
312	<i>Shatavari</i>
313	<i>Maha shatavari</i>
314	<i>Hapusha</i>
315	<i>Dhataki</i>
316	<i>langali</i>
317	<i>Giri karnika</i>
318	<i>Lajjalu</i>
319	<i>Shammi</i>
320	<i>Babbula</i>
321	<i>Aabhav babbula</i>
322	<i>Kakilaksh</i>
323	<i>Nadi kanta</i>
324	<i>Karpasi</i>
325	<i>Vatpatri</i>
326	<i>Brhm soma</i>
327	<i>Dev gandha</i>
328	<i>vrish gandha</i>
329	<i>Parpata</i>
330	<i>Hilmochika</i>
331	<i>Harida</i>
332	<i>Daru haridra</i>
333	<i>Amragandi haridra</i>
334	<i>Aativisha</i>
335	<i>Katuka</i>
336	<i>Rodhra</i>
337	<i>Yastimadhu</i>
338	<i>Karkatshringi</i>
339	<i>bharangi</i>

340	<i>Kataphala</i>
341	<i>Kataka</i>
342	<i>Pashan bhed</i>
343	<i>Vidanga</i>
344	<i>Shunthi</i>
345	<i>Aadraka</i>
346	<i>Maricha</i>
347	<i>Pippali</i>
348	<i>trikatua</i>
349	<i>Pippalimoola</i>
350	<i>Chavya</i>
351	<i>Gajapippali</i>
352	<i>Chitraka</i>
353	<i>Panchakola g</i>
354	<i>Jiraka</i>
355	<i>Shatapushpa</i>
356	<i>dhanyaka</i>
357	<i>Mishreya</i>
358	<i>Ajamoda</i>
359	<i>yavani</i>
360	<i>Parsik yavani</i>
361	<i>Aja gandha</i>
362	<i>Hingu</i>
363	<i>bashpika</i>
364	<i>Vacha</i>
365	<i>Lashuna</i>
366	<i>Palandu</i>
367	<i>Grijan</i>
368	<i>Eraka</i>
369	<i>Niladurva</i>
370	<i>Shvetadurva</i>
371	<i>gandadurva</i>
372	<i>Kasa</i>
373	<i>darbha</i>
374	<i>Munja</i>
375	<i>Ka trinam</i>
376	<i>bhustrin</i>
377	<i>Vetraka</i>
378	<i>Balvaja</i>
379	<i>Chandana</i>

380	<i>Raktachandana</i>
381	<i>Pitachandana</i>
382	<i>Kairatachandana</i>
383	<i>Aguru</i> (<i>Krishnaguru</i>)
384	<i>Tagara</i>
385	<i>Karpura</i>
386	<i>Apakav Karpura</i>
387	<i>Ishavas Karpura</i>
388	<i>Hima Karpura</i>
389	<i>Potashraya Karpura</i>
390	<i>Bhaskara Karpura</i>
391	<i>Parna Karpura</i>
392	<i>Chinaka Karpura</i>
393	<i>Kasturi</i>
394	<i>Kasturi Pariksha</i>
395	<i>Lata Kasturi</i>
396	<i>Marjari</i> (<i>Gandhamarjara</i>)
397	<i>Kumkkum</i>
398	<i>Silhak</i>
399	<i>Devadaru</i>
400	<i>Sarala</i>
401	<i>Shrivasa (Sarala</i> <i>Niryasa)</i>
402	<i>Kushtha</i>
403	<i>Pushkara moola</i>
404	<i>Elvalluk</i>
405	<i>Jatiphala</i>
406	<i>Jatipatri</i>
407	<i>Kankola</i>
408	<i>Lavanga</i>
409	<i>Varanga</i>
410	<i>Patraka</i>
411	<i>Shukhma ela</i>
412	<i>Bhadra ela</i>
413	<i>Nagakeshara</i>
414	<i>Trijataka</i>
415	<i>Renuka</i>
416	<i>Priyangu</i>

417	<i>Mustaka</i>
418	<i>Paripellav</i>
419	<i>Mamsi</i>
420	<i>Balaka</i>
421	<i>Ushira</i>
422	<i>lamanjakkka</i>
423	<i>Tumbaru</i>
424	<i>Kustumbaru</i>
425	<i>Stheneyak</i>
426	<i>Taalish</i>
427	<i>chorak</i>
428	<i>Mura</i>
429	<i>Kachura</i>
430	<i>Shati</i>
431	<i>Granthi parna</i>
432	<i>Saprikka</i>
433	<i>Nalika</i>
434	<i>Padmaka</i>
435	<i>Prapondarika</i>
436	<i>Guggulu</i>
437	<i>Guggulu Bheda</i>
438	<i>Lakshana Guggulu</i>
439	<i>Surala (Rala)</i>
440	<i>Majistha</i>
441	<i>Parpati</i>
442	<i>Patanga</i>
443	<i>Laksha</i>
444	<i>Sthula kamala</i>
445	<i>Padmini</i>
446	<i>Kamal</i>
447	<i>Nilotpala</i>
448	<i>Kumuda</i>
449	<i>Kalhara</i>
450	<i>Kinjalkam</i>
451	<i>Padmabijam</i>
452	<i>Variparni</i>
453	<i>Mallika</i>
454	<i>Malati</i>

Dhatu Varga^[9]

Sr. No.	Drug Name
1	<i>Suvarna</i>
2	<i>Rajata</i>
3	<i>Tamra</i>
4	<i>Kamsya</i>
5	<i>Vartaloha</i>
6	<i>Pittala</i>
7	<i>Nagavanga</i>
8	<i>Lauha</i>
9	<i>Parada</i>
10	<i>Abhraka</i>
11	<i>Gandhaka</i>
	<i>makhika</i>
12	<i>Manashila</i>
13	<i>Haratala</i>
14	<i>Gairika</i>
15	<i>Tuttha</i>
16	<i>Kasisa</i>
17	<i>Hingula</i>
18	<i>Shilajatu</i>
19	<i>Sindhura</i>

20	<i>Sauviranjana</i>
21	<i>Rasanjana</i>
22	<i>Pushpanjana</i>
23	<i>Saurastri mritika</i>
24	<i>Krishna mritika</i>
25	<i>Kardam</i>
26	<i>Hastimada</i>
27	<i>Boola</i>
28	<i>Gorochana</i>
29	<i>Sheleya</i>
30	<i>Nakha</i>
31	<i>Saindhav lavana</i>
32	<i>Sauvarchala Lavana</i>
33	<i>Krishna lavana</i>
34	<i>Vida Lavana</i>
35	<i>Samudra Lavana</i>
36	<i>Audbhida Lavana</i>
37	<i>Romaka Lavana</i>
38	<i>panshula Lavana</i>
39	<i>Kancha Lavana</i>
40	<i>Lavana bhed prayoga</i>

41	<i>Yavakshara</i>
42	<i>Swarjika kshara</i>
43	<i>Samanya kshara guna</i>
44	<i>Tankana kshara</i>
45	<i>Usa kshara</i>
46	<i>Gukshura palash kshara</i>
47	<i>Samudra fen</i>
48	<i>Shanka shudr a shankha</i>
49	<i>Ratana</i>
50	<i>Moktika</i>
51	<i>Markata</i>
52	<i>Ratana guna</i>
53	<i>Rajavarta</i>
54	<i>Vaikranta</i>
55	<i>Khatik</i>
56	<i>Sudha pashana</i>
57	<i>baluka</i>

Dhanya Varga^[10]

Sr. No.	Drug Name
1	<i>Dhanya bhed</i>
2	<i>Shali</i>
3	<i>Shali Bheda</i>
4	<i>Shali Jati</i>
5	<i>Shali samanya guna</i>
6	<i>Shali samanya guna</i>
7	<i>Rodra shukka</i>
8	<i>Dirgha shukka</i>
9	<i>dirgha naal</i>
10	<i>Kukutanda</i>
11	<i>Sar mukha</i>
	<i>Patanga</i>
12	<i>Langala</i>
13	<i>Raur</i>
14	<i>Shuknahat</i>
15	<i>Suchi much</i>

16	<i>Paravat</i>
17	<i>Tapaniya</i>
18	<i>Pundarik</i>
19	<i>Shastik brihi dhanya</i>
20	<i>Patala brihi</i>
21	<i>Chiin shali</i>
22	<i>Vapya shalli</i>
23	<i>Sthalaj shalli</i>
24	<i>Dagdha bhumi jat dhanya</i>
25	<i>Roopit dhanya</i>
26	<i>Yava</i>
27	<i>Godhuma</i>
28	<i>Godhuma Bheda</i>
29	<i>Shimbi dhnya bhed</i>
30	<i>Mudga</i>
31	<i>Mudga bhed</i>
32	<i>Masha</i>

33	<i>Rajmash</i>
34	<i>Makustha</i>
35	<i>Nishpav</i>
36	<i>Vallishimb</i>
37	<i>Satin</i>
38	<i>Harenu</i>
39	<i>Kalaya</i>
40	<i>Chanaka</i>
41	<i>Masura</i>
42	<i>Tuvari (Adhaki)</i>
43	<i>Kulattha</i>
44	<i>Kulathika</i>
45	<i>Tila</i>
46	<i>Atasi</i>
47	<i>Kusumbha</i>
48	<i>Sanpushpa</i>
49	<i>Trin dhanaya</i>
50	<i>Priyangu</i>

51	<i>Chinaka prabhitya</i>
52	<i>Sharbeeja</i>

53	<i>Yavanala</i>
54	<i>Gavedhuka</i>

55	<i>Paribhasha</i>
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Drava Varga^[11]

Sr. No.	Drug Name
1	<i>Toya Varga</i>
2	<i>Chaturvidh Jala</i>
3	<i>Ashta Vidha Jala</i>
4	<i>Atapa Jala Guna</i>
5	<i>Jangala Jala Guna</i>
6	<i>Sadharana Jala Guna</i>
7	<i>Nadeya Jala Guna</i>
8	<i>Samanya Nadi Jala Guna</i>
9	<i>kwathit Jala Guna</i>
10	<i>Dugdha nama guna</i>
11	<i>Dugdha samanya guna</i>
12	<i>godugdha guna</i>
13	<i>Krishnadi godugdha guna</i>
14	<i>Vashkayinan godugdha guna</i>
15	<i>vivatsa godugdha guna</i>
16	<i>Aja dugdha guna</i>
17	<i>Mrigya dugdha guna</i>
18	<i>Mahish Dugdha Guna</i>
19	<i>Nari Dugdha Guna</i>
20	<i>Ebh Dugdha Guna</i>
21	<i>ghotaki Dugdha Guna</i>
22	<i>Ekashapha Dugdha Guna</i>
23	<i>Austhra Dugdha Guna</i>
24	<i>Avika Dugdha Guna</i>

25	<i>Dharanadi Vishesh Guna</i>
26	<i>Nindit Dugdha Lakshana</i>
27	<i>Go Dugdha Sewana Kala Vibhaga Guna</i>
28	<i>Patra Vishesh Dugdha Guna</i>
29	<i>Santanika</i>
30	<i>Piyusha</i>
31	<i>Morata</i>
32	<i>Dadhikurchika</i>
33	<i>Takrakurchika</i>
34	<i>Ksheerashaka</i>
35	<i>Kilata-Takra-pindanam Lakshana</i>
36	<i>Dadhi Bheda</i>
37	<i>Manda Dadhika Lakshana</i>
38	<i>Dadhi Samanya Guna</i>
39	<i>Manda Dadhika Guna</i>
40	<i>Go Dadhi Guna</i>
41	<i>Aja Dadhi Guna</i>
42	<i>Mahisha Dadhi Guna</i>
43	<i>Nari Dadhi Guna</i>
44	<i>Hasti Dadhi Guna</i>
45	<i>Karabha Dadhi Guna</i>
46	<i>Avika Dadhi Guna</i>
47	<i>Galit Dadhi Guna</i>
48	<i>Nissara dagdh janit Dadhi Guna</i>
49	<i>ritu Visheshana Dadhi Guna</i>

50	<i>Vidhimantaren Dadhi sevanGuna</i>
51	<i>Dadhi Sara mastuni Guna</i>
52	<i>Takra Bheda</i>
53	<i>Gavya Takra Guna</i>
54	<i>Mahisha Takra Guna</i>
55	<i>Chhaga Takra Guna</i>
56	<i>Dosha Visheshana Takra Guna</i>
57	<i>Pakva Apakva Takra Guna</i>
58	<i>Takra Nishedha</i>
59	<i>Takra Sevana</i>
60	<i>Sadyo Nisarita Navaneeta Guna</i>
61	<i>Navaneeta Samanya Guna</i>
62	<i>Govya Navaneeta Guna</i>
63	<i>Mahisha Navaneeta Guna</i>
64	<i>Aja Navaneeta Guna</i>
65	<i>Avika Navaneeta Guna</i>
66	<i>Khirothan Navaneeta Guna</i>
67	<i>Sadhya skan Navaneeta Guna</i>
68	<i>Samanya Ghrita Guna</i>
69	<i>Go Ghrita Guna</i>
70	<i>Aja Ghrita Guna</i>
71	<i>Mahisha Ghrita Guna</i>
72	<i>Nari Ghrita Guna</i>

73	<i>Abhva Ghrita Guna</i>
74	<i>Eka Shapha Ghrita Guna</i>
75	<i>Karabh Ghrita Guna</i>
76	<i>Avika Ghrita Guna</i>
77	<i>Dugdha nihsrit Ghrita Guna</i>
78	<i>Purana Ghrita Guna</i>
79	<i>Kaumbhasarpi Mahaghrita</i>
80	<i>Ghrita Mandasya Guna</i>
81	<i>Taila Samanya Guna</i>
82	<i>Eranda Taila Guna</i>
83	<i>Sarshapa Taila</i>
84	<i>Atasi Taila</i>
85	<i>Kusumbha Taila</i>
86	<i>Karanja nimba Taila</i>
87	<i>Bhallatka tuvraka Taila</i>
88	<i>Ikashika Taila</i>
89	<i>Yavatikta Taila</i>
90	<i>Aamra Taila</i>
91	<i>Ingudi Taila</i>
92	<i>Devadarvadi tail</i>
93	<i>Sarja rasa tail</i>

94	<i>Bilwa tail</i>
95	<i>Vibhitaka tail</i>
96	<i>Madhuka tail</i>
97	<i>Shankhini tail</i>
98	<i>Ankol tail</i>
99	<i>Trivrit tail</i>
100	<i>Kapith tail</i>
101	<i>Dantayadi tail</i>
102	<i>Akshyadi tail</i>
103	<i>Saraladi tail</i>
104	<i>Madhukadi tail</i>
105	<i>Trapushadi tail</i>
106	<i>Sneh chatustyam</i>
107	<i>Madya Guna</i>
108	<i>Madya prakara</i>
109	<i>Navpurana Madhya guna</i>
110	<i>Madyapana Nishedha</i>
111	<i>Sura</i>
112	<i>Suravarunyo lakshana</i>
113	<i>Suraya Guna</i>
114	<i>Varunya Guna</i>
115	<i>Vibhitaka sura</i>
116	<i>Yava sura</i>
117	<i>Madhulaka</i>
118	<i>Draksha Sura</i>
119	<i>Kharjura Sura</i>
120	<i>Sharkara</i>
121	<i>Madhyasava</i>

122	<i>Gaud Madhya</i>
123	<i>Sidhu bheda</i>
124	<i>Jambhavasava</i>
125	<i>Surasava</i>
126	<i>Arista</i>
127	<i>Shukta</i>
128	<i>Shukta bheda</i>
129	<i>Gud shukta</i>
130	<i>Madhu shukta</i>
131	<i>Shandaki lakshana</i>
132	<i>Dhanyamala guna</i>
133	<i>Sauvurodaka tushodaka guna</i>
134	<i>Sauvurodaka guna</i>
135	<i>Kanjikasya lakshana</i>
136	<i>Samanya Mutra Guna</i>
137	<i>Mutra Samanya paribhasha</i>
138	<i>Gomutra Guna</i>
139	<i>Chag mutra Guna</i>
140	<i>Avika Mutra</i>
141	<i>Mahisha Mutra</i>
142	<i>Naga Mutra Guna</i>
143	<i>Ashwa Mutra Guna</i>
144	<i>Karabha Mutra Guna</i>
145	<i>Rasab Mutra Guna</i>
146	<i>Nara Mutra Guna</i>
147	<i>Goshkrita Guna</i>

Krita-Anna Varga^[13]

Sr. No.	Drug Name
1	<i>Odana</i>
2	<i>Odana Bheda</i>
3	<i>Truna Dhanya Odana</i>
4	<i>Mudga Odana</i>
5	<i>Yavagu</i>
6	<i>Krishara</i>
7	<i>Khichha</i>

8	<i>Payasa</i>
9	<i>Vilepi</i>
10	<i>Peya</i>
11	<i>Samanya Manda Guna</i>
12	<i>Shali manda</i>
13	<i>Vatya manda</i>
14	<i>Asta guna manda</i>
15	<i>Manda Bheda</i>
16	<i>yusha</i>

17	<i>Masuradi yusha</i>
18	<i>Kulatha panch yusha</i>
19	<i>Aranya Mudaga yusha</i>
20	<i>Kulath yusha</i>
21	<i>Aadhaki yusha</i>
22	<i>Chanaka yusha</i>
23	<i>Masura yusha</i>
24	<i>Masha yusha</i>

25	<i>Nishpava yusha</i>
26	<i>Pancha musti yusha</i>
27	<i>Navaanga yusha</i>
28	<i>Supa</i>
29	<i>Supa Guna</i>
30	<i>Raga Shadava</i>
31	<i>Shikhariṇi</i>
32	<i>Panaka</i>
33	<i>Panchsara panaka</i>
34	<i>Satakam</i>
35	<i>Bhaksha</i>
36	<i>Vishyandanam</i>
37	<i>Ghritpura</i>

38	<i>Madhushirshaka</i>
39	<i>Sanyava</i>
40	<i>Lapsika</i>
41	<i>Kulmash</i>
42	<i>Mandak-pupalika-angar karkati</i>
43	<i>Pupa</i>
44	<i>Shaskuli</i>
45	<i>Parpata</i>
46	<i>Lajja-dhana</i>
47	<i>Saktava</i>
48	<i>Mantha</i>
49	<i>Prithuka</i>
50	<i>Ouluka</i>

51	<i>Lumbika</i>
52	<i>Pista mansam</i>
53	<i>Parishushka mansam</i>
54	<i>Shulya mansam ghrit sidh mansam</i>
55	<i>Mansepak bheda</i>
56	<i>Saurav khanishka</i>
57	<i>Dak lavnika</i>
58	<i>Kwathita</i>
59	<i>Panchkoladi kwathita</i>
60	<i>Pinyaka pall</i>
61	<i>parpata</i>

Mamsa Varga^[12]

Sr. No.	Drug Name
1	<i>Mamsa Bheda</i>
2	<i>Jangala Mamsa Bheda</i>
3	<i>Anupa Mamsa Bheda</i>
4	<i>Jangala Gana</i>
5	<i>Vishikira Mamsa</i>
6	<i>Pratuda</i>
7	<i>Guhashya</i>
8	<i>Prasaha</i>
9	<i>Bilesha</i>
10	<i>Gramya</i>
11	<i>Parna mrina</i>
12	<i>Kulechara</i>
13	<i>Pallava</i>
14	<i>Koshastha</i>
15	<i>Matsya</i>
16	<i>Hasti</i>
17	<i>Hastiraja</i>
18	<i>Ashva nama Guna</i>
19	<i>Ashvatara namaGuna</i>
20	<i>Ustra nama Guna</i>
21	<i>Gardabha</i>

22	<i>Aja</i>
23	<i>Mesha</i>
24	<i>Mahisha</i>
25	<i>Vrishabh</i>
26	<i>Gou</i>
27	<i>Singh shadulashch</i>
28	<i>Vyaghro mahavyaghra</i>
29	<i>Vrika</i>
30	<i>Shwa</i>
31	<i>Shukara</i>
32	<i>Bidala</i>
33	<i>Nakula</i>
34	<i>Mushaka</i>
35	<i>Chuchundari</i>
36	<i>Vaanara</i>
37	<i>Shregal</i>
38	<i>Swalapa Shregal</i>
39	<i>Shalyaka</i>
40	<i>Mriga</i>
41	<i>Ena</i>
42	<i>Chitra harina</i>
43	<i>Bhaluka</i>
44	<i>Gokarna shambara</i>
45	<i>Mrigamatriaka</i>
46	<i>Kasturi Mriga</i>

47	<i>Kritmala</i>
48	<i>Shalabh</i>
49	<i>Shavadanshra</i>
50	<i>ruru</i>
51	<i>Nayanku</i>
52	<i>Shashaka</i>
53	<i>Pakshina</i>
54	<i>Hansa</i>
55	<i>Sarasa</i>
56	<i>Chakra vaka</i>
57	<i>Aati</i>
58	<i>Kadanka</i>
59	<i>Mayura</i>
60	<i>Bhramara</i>
61	<i>Shooka</i>
62	<i>Sarika</i>
63	<i>Kukuta</i>
64	<i>Kaka</i>
65	<i>Kaka Bheda</i>
66	<i>Bhasa</i>
67	<i>Gridha</i>
68	<i>Parawata</i>
69	<i>Manjughosa</i>
70	<i>Krikara</i>
71	<i>Kokila</i>
72	<i>Ulluka</i>

73	<i>Balgulika</i>
74	<i>Kasthakrutaka</i>
75	<i>chataka</i>
76	<i>Bharadwaja</i>
77	<i>Chasha</i>
78	<i>Shasghani</i>
79	<i>Shayena</i>
80	<i>Khajarita</i>
81	<i>Kukubha</i>
82	<i>Kalachataka</i>
83	<i>Latta</i>
84	<i>Chakora</i>
85	<i>Koncha</i>
86	<i>Pakshi Bheda</i>
87	<i>Ghumyata</i>
88	<i>Mahika Bheda</i>
89	<i>Bhringika</i>
90	<i>Indragopa</i>
91	<i>Lava</i>

92	<i>Tittiri Bheda</i>
93	<i>Chataka</i>
94	<i>Vritika</i>
95	<i>Sarpa</i>
96	<i>Ajagara</i>
97	<i>Dundubha</i>
98	<i>Rajasarpa</i>
99	<i>Jahaka</i>
100	<i>Sarpa Bheda</i>
101	<i>Godha</i>
102	<i>Gondupada</i>
103	<i>Kriklasa</i>
104	<i>Vrischika</i>
105	<i>Vrischika (Kambaliya Bheda)</i>
106	<i>Jaluka</i>
107	<i>Grehgodhika</i>
108	<i>Markata</i>
109	<i>Matsya</i>

110	<i>Rohita</i>
111	<i>Pathino Mahamatsya</i>
112	<i>Shaphari (Kshudra Matsya)</i>
113	<i>Krishna Matsya</i>
114	<i>Matsya Bheda</i>
115	<i>Shishumar</i>
116	<i>Nakra</i>
117	<i>Kachapa</i>
118	<i>Karkata</i>
119	<i>Manduka</i>
120	<i>Udbhava Bheda Matsya Guna</i>
121	<i>Nadhya Matsya</i>
122	<i>Karkata Mamsa Guna</i>

Vihara Varga^[14]

S. no	Drug Name
1	<i>Dinacharya</i>
2	<i>Achamana</i>
3	<i>Dantadhavana</i>
4	<i>Dantadhavana Bheda</i>
5	<i>Nirdishta Dantakashta</i>
6	<i>Drishhti Prasadana Shalaka</i>
7	<i>Anjana</i>
8	<i>Mukha Netra Prakshalana</i>
9	<i>Gandusha</i>
10	<i>Mukhashoshghana Gandusha</i>
11	<i>Dhumapana</i>
12	<i>Tambula Sevana</i>
13	<i>Gandusha malyanishhepana</i>
14	<i>Pushpadi dharana</i>

15	<i>Nishidh Malaya</i>
16	<i>Vastra dharana</i>
17	<i>Varabanama</i>
18	<i>Vastranishedha</i>
19	<i>Hastabharana dharana</i>
20	<i>Vastra Dharana Guna</i>
21	<i>Mauktika</i>
22	<i>Padamraga</i>
23	<i>Indraneela</i>
24	<i>Markata</i>
25	<i>Ratna Dharana Phala</i>
26	<i>Chatra Dharana Guna</i>
27	<i>danda Dharana Guna</i>
28	<i>Vyayama</i>
29	<i>Abhyanga</i>
30	<i>Shiro abhyanga</i>
31	<i>Snaha karna purana</i>
32	<i>Pada Abhyanga</i>

33	<i>Abhyanga</i>
34	<i>Udvardhana</i>
35	<i>Snana</i>
36	<i>Anulepana</i>
37	<i>Devpujana</i>
38	<i>Ahara</i>
39	<i>Anupana</i>
40	<i>Anupana Nishedha</i>
41	<i>Nishidh aana jana</i>
42	<i>Aanadi guna</i>
43	<i>Danta shodhana</i>
44	<i>Shayana vidhi</i>
45	<i>Nidroplabdhhi</i>
46	<i>Niyat samaya nidra aagamanupaya</i>
47	<i>Vyavaya</i>
48	<i>Vatadhya</i>
49	<i>Abadhkaramo Vihara</i>
50	<i>Sadhya Pranakarani</i>
51	<i>sadhya Pranaharani</i>
52	<i>Kalaakal mrityava</i>

Mishraka Varga^[15]

Sr. No.	Drug Name
1	<i>Trijataka chaturjata</i>
2	<i>Trikarshik chaturbhadra trimadhur</i>
3	<i>Samatrika</i>
4	<i>Triphala bheda</i>
5	<i>Madhyama Panchamula Jeevan Panchamula</i>
6	<i>Trin Panchamula</i>
7	<i>valli Panchamula kantaka Panchamula</i>
8	<i>Panchanga dasanga</i>
9	<i>Panchapallav</i>
10	<i>Panchanimba</i>
11	<i>Panchagavya</i>
12	<i>Panch loha-lohastaka</i>
13	<i>Sarva aushadhi</i>
14	<i>Sugandha Pancahaka</i>
15	<i>Adhyapushpa</i>
16	<i>Kshara Trayam</i>
17	<i>Kshara Panchaka</i>
18	<i>Kshara Saptaka</i>
19	<i>Kshara Ashtaka</i>
20	<i>Eka Dvi Tri Chatur Panch Lavana</i>
21	<i>Matrastaka</i>
22	<i>Panchakarma</i>
23	<i>Paribhasha</i>
24	<i>Aushadha Kalpana</i>
25	<i>Swarasa</i>
26	<i>Kalka</i>
27	<i>Kwatha</i>
28	<i>Yavagu</i>
29	<i>Hima</i>
30	<i>Phanta</i>
31	<i>Kalaka</i>

32	<i>Churna</i>
33	<i>Kusmanda khanda</i>
34	<i>Avaleha</i>
35	<i>Asav-arista</i>
36	<i>Bhaishaj matraavidhan</i>
37	<i>Kseerpaka</i>
38	<i>bhawana Vidhi</i>
39	<i>tandulodaka</i>
40	<i>Vaman-virechan kwathadi</i>
41	<i>Vamana Vega</i>
42	<i>Virechana Vega</i>
43	<i>Niruha Basti</i>
44	<i>Anuvasana Basti</i>
45	<i>Pratimarsha</i>
46	<i>Nasya Vidhi</i>
47	<i>Karna Purana Vidhi</i>
48	<i>Gandusha Vidhi</i>
49	<i>Pratisarana</i>
50	<i>Mukhalepa</i>
51	<i>Alepa</i>
52	<i>Putra Paka Vidhi</i>
53	<i>Kshara Vidhi</i>
54	<i>Shonit srava</i>
55	<i>Matra Nirdharana</i>
56	<i>Deepana</i>
57	<i>Pachana</i>
58	<i>Deepana Pachana</i>
59	<i>Sanshamana</i>
60	<i>Santrasana</i>
61	<i>bhedana</i>
62	<i>Virechana</i>
63	<i>Vamana</i>
64	<i>Sanshodhan</i>
65	<i>Chedana</i>
66	<i>lekhana</i>
67	<i>Grahi</i>
68	<i>Stambhana</i>
69	<i>Vaya sthapana</i>
70	<i>Rasayana</i>
71	<i>Vajikarana</i>

72	<i>Sukshma</i>
73	<i>Vayvaya-vikasi</i>
74	<i>Ahaladana</i>
75	<i>Hridyam</i>
76	<i>Medhyama</i>
77	<i>Abhishyandi</i>
78	<i>Anabhishyandi</i>
79	<i>Tripti</i>
80	<i>Tarpan</i>
81	<i>Priran</i>
82	<i>Balya</i>
83	<i>Shukrala</i>
84	<i>Vrishya</i>
85	<i>Abhishyandi</i>
86	<i>Lekhana</i>
87	<i>Galpana</i>
88	<i>Rasa</i>
89	<i>Vish-vishbheda</i>
90	<i>Sthavar vish</i>
91	<i>Jangam vish</i>
92	<i>Dushi vish</i>
93	<i>anuvasana</i>
94	<i>niruha</i>
95	<i>Utter basti</i>
96	<i>Netra prasadan</i>
97	<i>dhuma</i>
98	<i>Swedan</i>
99	<i>Phal varti</i>
100	<i>Sanskar</i>
101	<i>Matrakal</i>
102	<i>Vyayama</i>
103	<i>Udvartana</i>
104	<i>Udgharshana</i>
105	<i>Abhyanga</i>
106	<i>Snana</i>
107	<i>Parisheka</i>
108	<i>Avgahana</i>
109	<i>Pratishyaya</i>
110	<i>Vatashonita</i>
111	<i>Udarda</i>
112	<i>Kshutam</i>
113	<i>Hallas-utklesh</i>

114	<i>Gaurav</i>
115	<i>Jambha</i>

116	<i>Klama</i>
117	<i>Kotha</i>

118	<i>Nidra</i>
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Speciality of *Kaiyadeva Nighantu*- *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* is a unique Ayurvedic lexicon distinguished by its concise, practical, and holistic approach to *Dravyaguna*. Unlike earlier *Nighantus* that mainly focused on medicinal plants, it integrates *Aushadha* (medicine), *Ahara* (diet), *Drava* (liquids), *Mamsa* (animal products) and *Vihara* (lifestyle) within a single framework, reflecting the comprehensive Ayurvedic concept of health.

A special feature of this text is its functional *Varga* classification, which is clinically oriented and easy to apply in practice. The inclusion of *Vihara Varga* highlights the importance of lifestyle and behaviour in disease causation and management, which is rarely elaborated in other *Nighantus*. The text also gives due importance to processed foods (*Krita-Anna*) and compound preparations (*Mishraka*), emphasizing that preparation methods influence drug action.

Overall, *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* stands out for its brevity with utility, integration of diet and lifestyle with therapeutics and focus on practical drug identification, making it especially valuable for students, teachers, and clinicians of *Ayurveda*.

Concept of *Pathya- Apathya* in *Kaiyadeva Nighantu*- *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* gives special importance to *Pathya* (wholesome) and *Apathya* (unwholesome) substances, reflecting the Ayurvedic principle that proper diet and lifestyle are as important as medicine in maintaining health and treating disease. Unlike many earlier *Nighantus* that mainly focus on nomenclature, *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* integrates therapeutics with dietary discipline, making it a clinically oriented text.

Pathya–Apathya* in Different *Vargas

S. No.	<i>Varga</i>	<i>Pathya</i> (Wholesome)	<i>Apathya</i> (Unwholesome)	Clinical Significance
1	<i>Aushadhi Varga</i> ^[8]	<i>Guduchi, Haritaki, Amalaki, Shatavari</i> (when properly indicated)	<i>Ati-tikshna, ati-ushna</i> or improper use of drugs	Supports rational drug selection and avoids dosha aggravation
2	<i>Dhatu Varga</i> ^[9]	<i>Swarna, Rajata, Tamra, Lauha</i>	-	Useful in Rasayana, rejuvenation therapy, and management of chronic and deficiency disorders
3	<i>Dhanya Varga</i> ^[10]	<i>Shashtika Shali, Yava, Godhuma, Mudga</i>	<i>Masha, Nishpava,</i> heavy and incompatible grains	Helps in planning therapeutic and convalescent diets
4	<i>Drava Varga</i> ^[11]	<i>Ushnodaka, Takra, Dugdha</i> (properly used), <i>Ghrita, Madhu</i>	<i>Ati-dadhi,</i> excessive <i>Madya,</i> cold or impure water	Liquids act as <i>Anupana</i> influencing drug action
5	<i>Mamsa Varga</i> ^[12]	<i>Aja Mamsa, Mriga Mamsa, Lava</i>	<i>Mahisha, Varaha,</i> excessively fatty meat	Advises judicious use of meat in disease and weakness
6	<i>Krita-Anna Varga</i> ^[13]	<i>Peya, Vilepi, Yavagu, Manda</i>	<i>Guru, Abhishyandi,</i> deep-fried foods	Highlights importance of food preparation and digestion

7	Vihara Varga ^[14]	Proper <i>Nidra</i> , regulated <i>Vyayama</i> , <i>Abhyanga</i> , <i>Snana</i>	<i>Ratrijagarana</i> , <i>Vega-dharana</i> , <i>Ativyayama</i>	Lifestyle correction as a key therapeutic measure
8	Mishraka Varga ^[15]	Balanced formulations like <i>Triphala</i> , <i>Trikatu</i> (as indicated)	Improper or excessive compound usage	Ensures safety in combined drug formulations

DISCUSSION

Kaiyadeva Nighantu represents an important phase in the evolution of Ayurvedic lexicons, it adopts a holistic framework, incorporating medicinal plants, food articles, liquids, animal products, lifestyle factors, and compound preparations. This integrated approach reflects the fundamental Ayurvedic concept that *Aushadha* (medicine), *Ahara* (diet), and *Vihara* (lifestyle) together determine health and disease.

The *Varga*-based classification of *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* is particularly significant. By organizing dravyas into *Aushadhi*, *Dhatu–Dhanya*, *Drava*, *Mamsa*, *Krita-Anna*, *Vihara* and *Mishraka Vargas*, the text provides a user-friendly structure that facilitates quick reference and rational application in clinical practice. The inclusion of *Vihara Varga* is a notable contribution, emphasizing behavioural and lifestyle factors as therapeutic and preventive tools, which is rarely elaborated in other classical *Nighantus*. Similarly, the attention given to *Krita-Anna* (processed foods) and *Mishraka* (compound preparations) underscores the importance of food preparation and formulation methods in modifying the effects of substances.

In *Kaiyadeva Nighantu*, special importance to *Pathya* (wholesome) and *Apathya* (unwholesome) substances is given, *Pathya* refers to those *dravyas*, foods, liquids, and activities that:

- Support *Agni* (digestive fire)
- Maintain *Dosha* balance
- Promote *Dhatu* nourishment
- Aid in disease recovery

Apathya denotes substances and behaviours that:

- Aggravate *Doshas*
- Impair digestion
- Obstruct *srotas*
- Delay or worsen disease conditions

The text presents *Pathya–Apathya* mainly through *Aushadhi*, *Dhanya*, *Drava*, *Krita-Anna*, *Mamsa* and *Vihara Vargas* indicating a comprehensive lifestyle-based therapeutic approach.

Special Features of *Pathya–Apathya* Description

- **Integrated Approach:** Diet, medicine, and lifestyle are treated as a single therapeutic unit.
- **Disease-Oriented Utility:** *Pathya–Apathya* is often implied rather than separately listed, requiring clinical understanding.
- **Practical Focus:** Emphasis on daily food habits rather than rare or exotic substances.
- **Preventive Value:** Highlights avoidance (*Apathya*) as equally important as prescription.

Significance in Modern Practice- *Kaiyadeva Nighantu's Pathya–Apathya* specifications support:

- Personalized dietary counselling
- Safe drug administration
- Lifestyle correction in chronic diseases

- Preventive and promotive health care

Although *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* does not provide elaborate pharmacological details as understood in modern terms, its concise descriptions and emphasis on *Pathya–Apathya* offer valuable guidance for clinical decision-making. Correlating these classical insights with contemporary botanical, nutritional, and pharmacological research can further enhance its relevance in present-day Ayurvedic practice.

CONCLUSION

Kaiyadeva Nighantu is a concise yet comprehensive Ayurvedic lexicon that successfully integrates medicine, diet, liquids, lifestyle and compound formulations within a single systematic framework. Its practical *Varga* classification, emphasis on *Pathya–Apathya*, and clarification of polysemous drug names make it especially useful for accurate *dravya* identification and rational therapeutic application. Even in the contemporary era, *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* remains a valuable reference for students, teachers, and clinicians. Reassessing and correlating its concepts with modern scientific understanding can strengthen evidence-based Ayurvedic practice while preserving the essence of classical knowledge.

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